

A NOVEL STRENGTH MODEL FOR UNIDIRECTIONAL FIBRE-REINFORCED COMPOSITES WITH REALISTIC FIBRE PACKINGS

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Keywords: *strength model, stress redistribution, stress concentrations, unidirectional*

1 General Introduction

Most fibre-reinforced composites can sustain increasing loads, even after extensive transverse cracking of the laminate. The continuous 0° fibres continue to carry the load and their failure generally coincides with the final composite failure. Understanding the failure behaviour of 0° fibres is vital for the widespread application of composite materials. This understanding can be improved by unidirectional longitudinal strength models. Many different approaches have been proposed, but most strength models consist of two parts. First, the stress redistribution after a fibre breakage is calculated. Those results are then incorporated into a model which takes into account the fibre strength distribution.

Two types of stress redistribution models exist in literature. The first type are shear lag models. These models result in analytical solutions, but are limited by their inherent assumptions. Nevertheless, they are useful for studying the influence of various parameters, such as matrix stiffness [1], matrix plasticity [2-4], and debonding of the fibre-matrix interface [4, 5]. The second type is a finite element model, which uses fewer assumptions and can therefore yield more accurate results than shear lag models. Unfortunately, some authors reduce the obtained stress field to a single value, being the stress concentration factor (SCF) in the crack plane [3, 6]. This approach does not make full use of the capabilities of the finite element method, as the information on the stress concentration profile along the fibres, is lost.

Most stress redistribution models use hexagonal or square fibre packings [6-8], even though some authors have stressed the importance of random fibre packings [9, 10]. In a recent work [11], the present authors demonstrated that the packing has a significant influence on the stress redistribution. The

influence on the result of strength models is, however, still unknown.

Most strength models in literature are based on Rosen's chain-of-bundles model [12]. A unidirectional composite is considered to be composed of a series of layers perpendicular to the fibres. This means each fibre is split up into fibre elements. Weibull strengths are then assigned to all fibre elements. The stress redistribution model is incorporated into the strength model to calculate the stresses when fibres start breaking.

This paper presents a new strength model for unidirectional composites. The stress redistributions in random and ordered packings are calculated using the finite element method. The obtained stress fields are then incorporated into a strength model for unidirectional composites. This model is the first strength model for realistic random fibre packings. It will be used to compare the effect of hexagonal, square and random fibre packings on the modelled composite strength.

2 Stress redistribution model

2.1 Model description

This study models unidirectional carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy composites. The finite element model for the stress redistribution uses the random fibre packing generator of Melro et al. [13]. This was adapted to include a criterion for the minimal distance between the fibres [11]. This distance is varied randomly between 2 and 2,1 times the fibre radius. The generator yields a square representative volume element, which is reduced to circular realisation with a diameter of twelve fibre radiuses. Fig. 1 depicts a realisation of such a random fibre packing with a fibre volume fraction of 70%. Some fibres are almost touching, while others are much farther apart. The number of nearest neighbours is not equal to six, as in hexagonal packings, but varies between four and seven.

The packings are extruded along the fibre direction to obtain a 3D finite element model. The model length is equal to 60 fibre radiuses. Fig. 2 depicts the resulting model with the applied boundary conditions. A displacement is applied on the entire top surface. Since both fibres and matrix are assumed to be linearly elastic, the applied strain will not influence the results and was chosen at 0.1%. Symmetry in the fibre direction is imposed on the entire bottom plane, except on the middle fibre. The middle fibre has a traction-free surface, which represent its broken nature. The lateral surface of the cylindrical model is kept traction-free as well.

The described results are based on carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy. The constituent properties of both materials are summarised in table 1, in which E_L is the longitudinal Young's modulus, E_T the transverse Young's modulus, ν_{LT} the longitudinal Poisson's ratio, G_{LT} the longitudinal shear modulus, and G_{TT} the transverse shear modulus. Linear elasticity and perfect bonding are assumed for fibre and matrix.

Once the stress fields are obtained, the average longitudinal fibre stress σ_{avg} is calculated on imaginary fibre cross-sections. The SCF is calculated by comparing σ_{avg} to the stress σ_∞ at infinity:

$$SCF = \frac{\sigma_{avg} - \sigma_\infty}{\sigma_\infty} \quad (1)$$

The model is chosen long enough so that the average fibre stress at the top plane can be used instead of σ_∞ .

2.2 Stress concentrations around a single broken fibre

The stress redistribution model yields the stress along the broken fibre and the intact fibres. An example of the stress concentration profile along an intact fibre is shown in fig. 3. Four characteristic location on this profile are calculated. Firstly, the maximum SCF is defined as the maximum in the stress profile. Please note that maximum SCF does not occur at the crack plane, but at a small distance from that plane. This has been previously described in [1, 6]. Secondly, the overload length is defined as the location where the SCF reaches zero for the first time. Next, the SCF becomes negative, as previously

explained in [6]. The third parameter is the minimum SCF. The final location is at 80% of the minimum SCF. These four characteristic locations are indicated in the stress profile in fig. 3. For each location, both the SCF and the relative distance from the crack plane are calculated.

These calculations are done for five realisations of random fibre packings, as well as one model for square and one for hexagonal fibre packings. The results are plotted as a function of the relative distance of the intact fibre from the broken fibre. Fig. 4 displays the maximum SCF, fig. 5 the overload length, and fig. 6 the minimum SCF.

Trend lines are fitted through the data points for the random fibre packings, which is needed to transfer these data to the strength model. Logarithmic or second order polynomial trend lines are used, depending on which one resulted in the best fit. Only intact fibres at a relative distance of less than four fibre radiuses are taken into account. The other intact fibres are not considered, as they carry a SCF close to zero.

The trend lines fit the data well, even though some discrepancies can be observed. The most important discrepancy occurs at distances larger than three fibre radiuses. The trend lines for maximum and minimum SCF cross the x-axis in fig. 4 and fig. 6. Since this is not observed in the FE data, the SCF is assumed to be zero when this occurs.

The data points for the regular fibre packings can also be found in fig. 4-6. These data points are directly inserted into the strength model, without a trend line. They follow the data for the random fibre packings, although some small differences may be observed. This, however, does not mean that the stress redistribution in regular and random packings is the same. A vital difference can be observed in fig. 4. The highest maximum SCF for the hexagonal packing is observed at 6.7%, while it is 13.8% for the random fibre packings. This observation can cause an overestimation in composite strength in models with hexagonal fibre packings. There is, however, another effect that counteracts this. The six nearest neighbours in the hexagonal packing carry the same SCF, as they are all at the same distance. The six nearest neighbours in a random fibre packing, however, are all at different distances and hence, do not carry the same SCF. Some of those 6 neighbours will carry a SCF larger than 6.7%, but

the others will carry a smaller SCF. The final influence on the strength model remains difficult to predict from an SCF analysis.

Based on the trend lines, the four characteristic points are predicted for random, square and hexagonal packings. The intermediate stress levels are then calculated in the strength model using piecewise linear interpolation, as illustrated in fig. 7.

2.3 Stress recovery in the broken fibre

A similar approach is used to capture the stress recovery in the broken fibre. The stress profile along the broken fibre is shown in fig. 8. Three characteristic locations are calculated; where 60% recovery, 90% recovery and 95% recovery is achieved.

Please note that a stress singularity exists close to the fracture surface of the broken fibre. Since this region is in principle also infinitely thin, a stress of 0 MPa is assumed in the fracture plane, which means that the interpolation in fig. 8 starts in the origin. The line between 90% and 95% recovery is extrapolated to 100%. Further away from the crack plane, the stress is assumed to be fully recovered.

These three stress recovery lengths are summarised in fig. 9 for the three different fibre packings at a fibre volume fraction of 70%. The random fibre packings consistently demonstrated a lower recovery length. This phenomenon has been explained in [11]. The random fibre packing has more fibres close to the broken fibre, locally resulting in a higher homogenised shear stiffness. This higher shear stiffness results in faster stress recovery, and hence shorter stress recovery lengths.

3 Strength model

3.1 General description

The strength model consists of 2000 fibres in random, square or hexagonal fibre packings. Each fibre is 150 fibre radiuses long and is divided into 300 fibre elements. The division into fibre elements is schematically represented in fig. 9.

A schematic overview of the strength model is provided in fig. 10. The model starts off by assigning a Weibull strength to each fibre element.

The fibre strength σ_f of fibre elements of length L

was characterised by the Weibull probability density function $F(\sigma_f)$:

$$F(\sigma_f) = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{L}{L_0}\right)\left(\frac{\sigma_f}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right], \quad (2)$$

in which m is the Weibull shape parameter, σ_0 the Weibull scale parameter and L_0 the length at which σ_0 was measured. The Weibull strength distribution of the carbon fibres is based on literature data: $\sigma_0 = 2700$ MPa, $m = 9.03$ and $L_0 = 100$ mm [14].

Next, the global strain is gradually incremented. After each strain increment, the model checks in every fibre element whether the stress has exceeded the strength. If this is the case, then the fibre element is considered to be broken and the stress in the surrounding fibre elements is updated based on the finite element stress redistribution, as discussed earlier. Since the stress concentrations may cause other fibres to break in the same strain increment, the model checks again whether any new fibres were broken. This is repeated until no new fibre was found broken in the current strain increment. Then, the failure criterion for the entire composite is checked. If the failure criterion is not reached, the strain is incremented and the process repeats itself. If the failure criterion is satisfied, then the model stops.

This failure criterion, as well as some other aspects, requires further elaboration. This is done in the subsequent sections.

3.2 Superposition for multiple fibre breaks

The stress redistribution model, which was presented earlier in this paper, only determined the stress redistribution around a single broken fibre. When the strain is increased, breaks will start accumulating and broken fibre clusters will develop. For an accurate prediction of cluster formation and final failure, a superposition principle is needed to predict stresses around multiple fibre breaks. In the current model, linear superposition is applied. This means that the SCFs for single fibre breaks are summed up to predict the SCFs around multiple broken fibres. Linear superposition is proposed as a good first approximation. In reality however, the broken fibres do start interacting with each [15].

3.3 Strain application

The strain on each plane of fibre elements is the same if all fibres are intact. When a fibre element is broken, the plane, in which that element is located, becomes more compliant. This means the strain in that plane should be larger than in the other planes. The application of the same strain on all planes, therefore, would be incorrect.

To solve this issue, the local strain on each plane is allowed to be different from the global strain. The average of all the local strains, however, has to be equal to the global strain. Since all fibre elements have the same length, this constraint imposes the sum of all the local displacements to be equal to the global displacement.

A rule was set up to implement this behaviour. The average SCF of the fibre elements is averaged on each plane. Since a broken fibre element has a SCF of zero, a plane with broken fibre elements will have a lower than average SCF. The inverse of this average SCF is used as a weighing factor. This means that a plane with more broken fibres will be subjected to a larger strain, as the inverse of the average SCF is higher. Even though this weighing procedure can be further refined, it does correctly represent the mechanics: strain localisation on the planes with more broken fibre elements.

3.4 Cluster development

To understand the fracture behaviour, it is useful to track the cluster development. Therefore, the model tracks all the broken fibre elements and calculates the size of all the clusters at each strain increment. Two broken fibre elements are considered to be part of the same cluster if:

- The surface-to-surface distance between the fibres is smaller than two times the fibre radius.
- The distance along the length is less than ten times the fibre radius.

3.5 Failure criterion

If one plane of elements is fully broken, then the local strain would become infinite, while the strain in the other planes would be zero. To avoid these numerical problems, a failure criterion is needed to stop the model. The model automatically stops if the global stress is 10% lower than the maximum global stress that was reached in all previous strain

increments. This criterion coincides with a vertical decrease in the stress.

4 Results

Fifteen models were run for each packing. Fig. 12 illustrates the general shape of the tensile diagrams. Deviations from linear elastic behaviour can only be observed in the last part of the tensile diagram. The large number of broken fibres is responsible for this deviation.

Fig. 13 plots the number of clusters up and till a cluster of 8 broken fibre elements for a random fibre packing. Fig. 14 multiplies that number by the size of the cluster. This yields the total number of elements which are part of each cluster size. From these figures, it is clear that 1-plets, which is an isolated broken fibre element, slowly start to develop around 1% strain. Cluster formation only starts at 1.6%, when the first 2-plets develop. Two remarkable features are noticeable. Firstly, the amount of 1-plets and 2-plets start to decrease near the failure strain, as those clusters develop into of larger clusters. Secondly, fig. 14 demonstrates that, at the final failure, the amount of broken fibre elements is roughly the same in each cluster size. Given the complex interactions between the broken fibres, it is likely that the last 0.1 to 0.2% strain is not accurately predicted.

The failure strain was calculated as the strain at which the maximum stress is reached. The average failure strains are summarised in fig. 15, while figure 16 gives their cumulative probability distribution. The modelled failure strains lie between 2.1% and 2.2%. This corresponds well with the results of Wang et al. [14], who used the same Weibull strength distribution.

Random fibre packings display a higher failure strain than regular packings. The difference is small, but statistically significant. The difference between the three packings is also visible in the probability distribution function in fig 16.

The square packing appears to be a more realistic representation of real packings than hexagonal packings. The failure strain of square packings is closer to the random packings than the failure strain of hexagonal packings. This can be understood from the more random nature of the square packings. While the hexagonal packing has six nearest neighbours, the square packing has only four. This is

also reflected in fig. 4-6, where hexagonal packings only has three data points, while square packings have five.

5 Conclusion

A novel strength model was developed, which is able to incorporate random fibre packings. The finite element method was used to calculate the stress redistribution after a single fibre breakage. Those results were incorporated into a separate strength model, which is able to track the cluster development.

The strength model proved that random fibre packings yield a small, but statistically significant difference in composite failure strain than regular packings. Square packings are preferred over hexagonal packings, as they more closely resemble random packings.

Future work will focus on improving the final failure prediction by refining the stress redistribution model with effects such as matrix plasticity and fibre-matrix debonding. The strength model will be extended to hybrid composites, to predict their complex tensile diagram.

Fig. 1. Example of a random fibre packing realisation with a fibre volume fraction of 70%.

Fig. 2. A 3D view of the finite element model with the boundary conditions in red. The lateral surface is traction-free.

Table 1. Engineering constants of the carbon fibre and epoxy matrix.

	Carbon fibre	Epoxy matrix
E_L (GPa)	230	3
E_T (GPa)	15	3
ν_{LT} (-)	0.25	0.4
G_{LT} (GPa)	13.7	1.07
G_{TT} (GPa)	6	1.07

Fig. 3. Example of the stress concentrations as a function of the relative distance from the crack plane.

Fig. 4. The maximum SCF as a function of the relative distance from the broken fibre.

Fig. 5. The overload length as a function of the relative distance from the broken fibre.

Fig. 6. The minimum SCF as a function of the relative distance from the broken fibre.

Fig. 7. Interpolation of the four characteristic locations in the stress profile of the intact fibres.

Fig. 8. Interpolation of the three characteristic locations in the stress profile of the broken fibre.

Fig. 9. Stress recovery lengths for the three packings at 70% fibre volume fraction.

Fig. 10. Random fibre packing with fibres split up into fibre elements

Fig. 11. Schematic overview of the strength model

Fig. 12. Example of a modelled stress-strain diagram

Fig. 13. Number of plets in a random fibre packing as a function of the applied strain.

Fig. 13. Number of fibre elements in each cluster size in a random fibre packing as a function of the applied strain.

Fig. 15. Comparison of the failure strains of the three types of packings. The error bars indicate the 95% confidence interval.

Fig. 16. Cumulative probability distribution function of the failure strains of the three types of packings.

Acknowledgements

The work leading to this publication has received funding from the European Union Seventh Framework Programme (FP7/2007-2013) under the topic NMP-2009-2.5-1, as part of the project HIVOCOMP (Grant Agreement No. 246389). The authors thank the Agency for Innovation by Science and Technology in Flanders (IWT) for the grant of Y. Swolfs. The authors also thank A.R. Melro, P.P.

Camanho and S.T. Pinho for the permission to use their random fibre packing generator. I. Verpoest holds the Toray Chair in Composite Materials at KU Leuven.

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